

Strategic Risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics Using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around strategic risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 1981 to 2022, by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Strategic Risk". Based on the search results, there were 89 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to strategic risk is divided into 13 clusters. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 11 main themes related to strategic risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Strategic Risk, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

INTRODUCTION

Risk management in financial institutions has improved in line with the development of the financial industry as a whole. In recent years, financial institutions have begun to understand the importance of risk management to maintain business stability and continuity. This can be seen from the existence of regulations from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) which regulate risk exposure management and effective corporate governance. Risks in the financial sector must be recognized and controlled by estimating the potential that may occur in the future, not after the risk has already occurred. Therefore, a methodology for modeling risks that may occur in the future is very important so that those making decisions can prepare strategies to overcome future risks. One of the risks that occurs in the financial industry is strategic risk. Strategic risk management involves identifying, assessing, controlling and monitoring these risks over time to ensure that the bank remains stable and maintains its reputation.

In previous research, strategic risk management involved various factors, including: (1) changes in the competitive landscape and business competition; (2) changes in regulations from policy makers; (3) errors in formulating business strategies so that they are not in line with the company's vision and mission; (4) lack of innovation in business product development; (5) not adapting to new technological advances; and (6) changes in global economic conditions, both micro and macro. In general, strategic risk arises from errors in strategic decision making by bank management, such as taking business risks, product diversification, geographic expansion, and others. This condition can cause potential losses in the banking industry. Therefore, banks must monitor and manage strategic risks well to ensure their business continuity and financial stability. There are several ways to mitigate strategic risk, including: (1) planning and implementing effective business strategies and adapting to changes in the business environment; (2) create a special team or division to develop new products and prepare several strategic plans; (3) ensure that the business strategy does not conflict with the institution's vision and mission; (4) collaborating with various parties related to company development.

Based on the problems above, strategic risk management topic mapping is needed to identify, measure and control risks that will occur. This can fulfill the need for human resources tasked with risk management to have knowledge, skills and work attitudes according to the bank's needs. So, the aim of this research is to map research topics around strategic risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature review study to analyze, identify and review articles from indexed international journals and accredited national journals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Strategic risk is the risk associated with making business decisions by companies, including banking, which can affect their future performance and have a negative impact on the company's profits, assets and reputation. This relates to the selection of specific products or markets, geographic expansion, new business development, and mergers and acquisitions. Strategic risks can cause a company to miss opportunities or make wrong business decisions that can affect long-term performance and require additional investment to improve the situation. In banking, strategic risk can include selecting the wrong marketing strategy, inadequate market penetration, or selecting products that do not match the customer's risk profile.

Bibliometric studies are a branch of science that analyzes and evaluates scientific publications and related information. It involves the use of statistical and informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in scientific literature. Bibliometric studies can be used to measure the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions and scientific fields, as well as to understand interactions and relationships between scientific fields and publications. It can also help in the identification and evaluation of trends and issues in the scientific literature. Some applications of bibliometric studies include citation network analysis, cluster analysis, and visibility analysis. Results from bibliometric studies can be used by researchers, government, and industry to understand developments and contributions in scientific fields and to determine future research directions.

VOSviewer is a bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of graphs and diagrams that are intuitive and easy to accept. VOSviewer can help researchers and analysts carry out citation network analysis, find relationships between scientific fields, and understand trends and issues in scientific literature. It also helps in determining future research directions and gaining insight into the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions, and scientific fields. VOSviewer has an easy-to-use user interface and can be used together with data coming from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. It allows users to visualize and analyze publication data effectively and efficiently.

Literature review is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic. It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research developments and directions. Literature review studies are usually conducted as part of the research process to ensure that researchers understand the existing research environment and produce non-duplicative results. It also helps in determining problems and gaps in the existing literature and helps in the formulation of hypotheses and understanding of specific research areas. Literature review studies can be carried out by accessing scientific publication databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Researchers can also carry out manual searches through scientific journals and related books. Literature review studies must be carried out with a systematic and objective methodology to ensure that the results are accurate and valid.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is strategic risk. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on strategic risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions.

The source of data collection comes from search for national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keyword " Strategic Risk " in the entire year period (1981 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific

publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics research based on literature review studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Strategic Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 89 international and national journals based on the results of data collection from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 1981 to 2022. There are 19 journals Scopus indexed international. And there is 70 international and national journals indexed by Sinta around strategic risk research.

Journal publication data regarding Legal Risk by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
1981-1998	8	2007	3	2013	5	2018	8
2001	1	2008	3	2014	3	2019	5
2002	2	2009	2	2015	5	2020	4
2004	1	2010	4	2016	6	2021	9
2005	1	2011	1	2017	7	2022	6
2006	1	2012	4				

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Strategic Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are several things that need to be considered when knowing bibliometric results with software VOSviewer, namely: first, the software interface, namely the VOSviewer interface displays diagrams and graphs that visualize publication data. Users can open and explore these charts and graphs by clicking on specific items or zooming in on specific parts of the diagram. Second, visual components, namely several visual components that may appear in VOSviewer bibliometric results includes nodes (representations of publications), lines (representations of citation relationships), and colors (representations of categories or topics). Third, citation network analysis, namely citation network analysis helps in determining relationships between publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Larger nodes in the diagram represent more widely noted publications and relationships between nodes can help in understanding how publications are related. Fourth, cluster analysis, namely cluster analysis helps in determining relationships between topics or fields of science and understanding how publications are related to certain topics or fields of science. The colors in the diagram represent categories or topics and help in understanding how publications relate to different topics or fields of science. Fifth, citation analysis, namely citation analysis helps in determining the most noted publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Larger nodes in the diagram represent more widely recorded publications and help in understanding how publications relate to each other. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around Strategic Risk

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer is related to the research development map regarding strategic risks in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, there are 13 clusters and 88 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 13 topic items, namely: banks, bank risk management, banking sector, banking system, basel iii, control, future, management, methodology, risk management, strategic direction, strategic planning, strategic risk.
- Cluster 2 consists of 12 topic items, namely: acquisition, bank merger, banking, competition, exposure, foreign bank, private banking, risk, strategic group, strategic risk management, strategy.
- Cluster 3, consists of 11 topic items, namely: central bank, China, e banking, India, risk concept, risk measure, sovereign wealth fund, strategic asset allocation, strategic framework, strategic investment, world bank.
- Cluster 4, consists of 10 topic items, namely: credit, deposits, depositors, guarantee trust bank plc, IDBI bank, industry, jeger, liquidity risk, strategic management, strategic positioning.
- Cluster 5, consists of 8 topic items, namely: commercial banks, competitive advantage, credit risk policy, downscaling, kenya, nic bank, sme sector, strategic choice.
- Cluster 6, consists of 6 topic items, namely: Canadian banking, evolution, paradigm, risk compliance, risk executive, strategic risk management.
- Cluster 7, consists of 6 topic items, namely: bank risk, bank equity capital result, risk level, strategic, trading book, violation.
- Cluster 8, consists of 5 topic items, namely: econpaper, entrepreneurial orientation, financial technology, rural banks, strategic alliance decisions.
- Cluster 9, consists of 5 topic items, namely: banking industry, effective strategic risk criteria, integrated strategic risk development, interpretive structural modeling approach, strategic goals.
- Cluster 10, consists of 4 topic items, namely: bank capital regulation, penalties, risk models, strategic selection.
- Cluster 11, consists of 3 topic items, namely: bank strategic planning, liability risk management.
- Cluster 12, consists of 3 topic items, namely: credit risk management, Indian banking sector.
- Cluster 13, consists of 2 topic items, namely: branch banking, infrastructure.

Mapping Literature Review around the Definition and Objectives of Strategic Risk Management

First, the definition of strategic risk. The findings in this research topic are:

- (1) Strategic risk is the risk associated with making business decisions by companies, including banking, which can affect their future performance and have a negative impact on the company's profits, assets and reputation. This relates to the selection of specific products or markets, geographic expansion, new business development, and mergers and acquisitions.
- (2) Strategic risks can cause a company to miss opportunities or make wrong business decisions that can affect long-term performance and require additional investment to improve the situation. In banking, strategic risk can include selecting the wrong marketing strategy, inadequate market penetration, or selecting products that do not match the customer's risk profile.

Second, the goal of strategic risk management is to help companies minimize the negative impact of wrong or unsuccessful business decisions, and help them achieve their long-term goals. This includes: (1) helping banks minimize business risks associated with making wrong business decisions; (2) ensuring that business decisions taken by banks are in line with their long-term goals and help them achieve their desired targets; (3) help banks develop effective business strategies and ensure that the business decisions taken have the potential for long-term profits; (4) ensure that banks are responsible and transparent in their business decision making and ensure that they can explain and account for the results of these decisions; and (5) help banks maintain their reputation and image by ensuring that the business decisions they make have a positive impact on society and the environment.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Supervision in Strategic Risk Management

Findings in this research topic include:

First, the authority and responsibilities of the Board of Commissioners, namely: (1) responsible for determining the company's long-term strategy and goals, including strategic risk management; (2) responsible for ensuring that banks have effective risk management systems and procedures, and ensure that strategic risk management is carried out effectively; (3) responsible for reviewing and evaluating the strategic risk management program and ensuring that the program is effective and in line with company objectives; (4) responsible for ensuring that banking is responsible and transparent in terms of strategic risk management and ensuring that business decisions taken can be justified; and (5) responsible for ensuring that strategic risk management is carried out with integrity and ensuring that banks do not engage in unethical or unlawful business practices.

Second, the authority and responsibilities of the Board of Directors, namely: (1) responsible for ensuring that the company's strategies and objectives, including strategic risk management, are implemented effectively; (2) responsible for ensuring that banks have effective risk management systems and procedures, and ensuring that strategic risk management is carried out appropriately; (3) responsible for setting appropriate risk limits for banks and ensuring that banks do not involve themselves in business activities that have high risks; (4) responsible for monitoring and evaluating risks associated with business decisions and ensuring that such risks are managed effectively; and (5) responsible for ensuring that banking is responsible and transparent in terms of strategic risk management and ensuring that business decisions taken can be justified.

Third, related to Human Resources, namely: (1) working together with the banking strategy team to develop and implement effective risk management strategies; (2) identify and analyze risks associated with business decisions and ensure that these risks are managed effectively; (3) monitor and evaluate risks associated with business decisions and ensure that such risks are managed effectively; (4) Human resources must be trained and sensitized towards strategic risk management and ensure that all banking employees understand their role in risk management; and (5) monitor and report strategic risk management results to the Board of Directors and Board of Commissioners.

Fourth, it relates to the Strategic Risk Management Organization/OMRS, which is the part of a bank that is responsible for monitoring and managing risks related to the bank's business activities. This ensures that banks can identify and manage risks effectively before they affect the bank's performance and stability. Strategic Risk Management Organization involves several tasks, such as: (1) Determining and identifying risks that may be related to the bank's business activities; (2) Assess risks and estimate potential losses that may occur; (3) Determine and implement strategies to manage and overcome risks;

- (4) Monitoring risks and monitoring the performance of the risk control strategies implemented; and
- (5) Send reports on risks and risk control to related parties, such as the Board of Directors and Board of Commissioners.

Mapping Literature Review around Strategic Risk Management Strategies

Findings in this research topic include:

First, banks can evaluate their competitive position in the industry by paying attention to strategic risks in several ways, including:

1. SWOT analysis, namely banks can use SWOT analysis to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that exist in the industry. This helps the Bank to determine how strategic risk affects its competitive position.
2. Competitor Analysis, namely the bank can compare its competitive position with its main competitors in the industry, paying attention to factors such as market, product, technology and strategy.
3. PESTEL analysis, namely banks can use PESTEL analysis to assess the impact of the political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental environment on their competitive position in the industry.
4. Product Differentiation Analysis, where the bank can assess how the products and services it offers differentiate it from competitors, and how this affects its competitive position in the industry.
5. Customer Analysis, namely the bank can assess the level of customer satisfaction and level of loyalty towards its products and services, and how this affects its competitive position in the industry.

Second, the bank establishes a written strategic plan and business plan through the following stages: (1) Evaluation of the current situation, namely the bank carries out internal and external analysis to determine its current position and identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT analysis); (2) Determining goals and strategies, namely the bank determines long-term goals and establishes a strategy to achieve them, which may involve product or market diversification, geographic expansion, or increasing operational efficiency; (3) Business planning, where the bank establishes specific business plans to achieve strategic goals, which may involve developing new products, improving customer service, or increasing cost efficiency; (4) Determining Budget and Resource Allocation, namely the bank determines the budget and resource allocation for each planned business initiative; and (5) Implement and Monitor, namely the bank implements business plans and strategies and carries out regular monitoring and evaluation to ensure that they are running according to plan and making necessary changes.

Third, banks are required to have sufficient funding sources to support the implementation of strategic plans. This funding source can be funds from the sale of banking products, loans or investments. Without stable and sufficient funding sources, banks cannot finance business initiatives and daily operations and meet regulatory obligations. Funding sources also influence a bank's ability to pursue business opportunities and meet market demands. Therefore, banks must ensure that they have quality and sufficient funding sources to achieve strategic goals and meet operational needs. Banks must also ensure that they have diversified funding sources and have a risk level that suits the bank's risk profile. This helps ensure long-term stability and minimizes the risk of funding failure.

Fourth, strategic plans and business plans must be evaluated regularly and can be adjusted if there are deviations. These evaluations help banks ensure that they are on track with long-term goals and make necessary changes to address problems or take advantage of new opportunities. This evaluation also helps banks ensure that strategic plans and business plans are still relevant and appropriate to the changing business environment. Economic, regulatory, or market changes may affect a bank's ability to achieve strategic objectives. Therefore, banks must evaluate and make necessary changes to ensure that they remain on the right track. With regular evaluation and updates, banks can ensure that their strategic plans and business plans help them achieve long-term goals and ensure long-term business stability and success.

Fifth, in the event that a bank plans to implement a long-term and sustainable strategy, the adequacy of the managerial succession plan is very important. Managerial succession planning helps ensure that the bank has leaders who have the right skills and qualifications to lead strategy

implementation and ensure continuity of operations. Managerial succession planning also ensures that the bank has thorough planning to ensure that the new leader can quickly and effectively lead operations and ensure that the strategy continues to work well despite management changes. This ensures that the bank can address any problems that may arise and ensure business continuity. Managerial succession planning also ensures that the bank has thorough planning to ensure that the new leader can quickly and effectively lead operations and ensure that the strategy continues to work well despite management changes. This ensures that the bank can address any problems that may arise and ensure business continuity.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Risk Levels, Policies, Procedures and Limits in Strategic Risk Management

Findings in this research topic include:

First, the level of risk to be taken (risk appetite) and risk tolerance (risk tolerance) are two very important concepts in strategic risk management in banking. These two concepts help banks determine how much risk they are prepared to take and how much risk they can tolerate. The level of risk to be taken (risk appetite), namely the level of risk to be taken shows how much risk the bank can take before reducing the value of the company. This is the level of risk that banks can accept in carrying out their operations and meeting their business objectives. Risk tolerance: Risk tolerance is how much risk a bank can accept before it has a significant impact on their operations and finances. It shows how much risk a bank can accept before they have to take action to address the risk.

Second, policy on strategic risk. Strategic risk policy in banking is part of bank risk management which focuses on controlling and managing risks originating from business activities and bank strategies. The aim of this policy is to ensure that banks can operate efficiently and profitably while minimizing risks that might threaten the continuity of their business. Some examples of strategic risk policies in banking include: (1) Business diversification policies, namely banks can expand their product and service portfolios to reduce business risks that come from focusing on one particular business area; (2) Portfolio management policies, namely banks can carry out careful management of their loan portfolios to ensure that credit risks are spread evenly; (3) Interest rate risk policy, namely banks can manage interest rate risk by ensuring that they have a balanced position in lending and funding activities with fixed interest rates and floating interest rates; and (4) Hedging policy, namely banks can hedge to limit market risks originating from fluctuations in asset prices or financial markets.

Third, procedures for strategic risk. Procedures for strategic risk in banking include several steps that ensure that the bank's business and strategic risks can be recognized, measured and controlled properly. The following are several steps in strategic risk procedures in banking: (1) Banks must identify risks originating from their business activities and strategies, through internal and external analysis and evaluation; (2) Once the risks are identified, the bank must determine the risk level for each risk by assessing the potential for loss and the frequency with which it may occur; (3) Banks must ensure that risks that have been identified and assessed can be controlled by establishing appropriate risk control strategies; (4) Banks must ensure that the risk control strategies implemented function well through regular supervision and monitoring; and (5) Banks must ensure that their strategic risk policies and procedures remain relevant and in synchronization with changes in the market and business environment by periodically revising and updating them.

Fourth, strategic risk limits. Strategic risk limits in banking are limits set by banks for each type of risk originating from their business activities and strategies. The purpose of strategic risk limits is to ensure that banks are not exposed to unacceptable levels of risk. Strategic risk limits in banking are important to ensure that banks operate safely and have a clear understanding of acceptable levels of risk. These risk limits can also help banks determine appropriate risk control strategies and ensure that they are not exposed to unacceptable levels of risk.

Mapping Literature Review around Strategic Risk Identification

Strategic risk identification in banking is a process for recognizing and assessing risks that affect a bank's business strategy. Strategic risks can include a variety of things, such as changes in the industry or market, changes in regulations, or changes in government policy. Findings in this research topic include:

- (1) regulatory risk, namely banks must ensure that they meet applicable regulatory requirements. Regulatory changes can affect banks' business strategies and require them to adapt their operations.
- (2) market risk, i.e. banks must monitor changes in the market and ensure that their business strategies remain relevant. This helps banks avoid market risks, such as price fluctuations or changes in interest rates.
- (3) technological risk, namely banks must ensure that they have the latest and most advanced technology to run their operations and meet customer needs. This helps banks meet technology requirements and ensures that they are not exposed to technology risks.
- (4) reputation risk, i.e. banks must ensure that they have a good reputation in society and the industry. This helps banks retain customers and meet stakeholder expectations.
- (5) financial risk, i.e. banks must ensure that they have sufficient resources to carry out their operations and meet their obligations. This helps banks avoid financial risks, such as liquidity or solvency.

Mapping Literature Review around Strategic Risk Measurement

Findings in this research topic include:

First, in measuring Strategic Risk, you can use indicators/parameters in the form of:

1. The level of complexity of a bank's business strategy is a measure of how complex and detailed the business strategy implemented by a bank is. This includes factors such as the number of products and services offered, the number of markets addressed, and the level of integration with different technologies and systems. The more products and services offered, the more markets addressed, and the higher the level of integration with technology, the higher the level of complexity of the bank's business strategy. Executing a complex business strategy requires careful planning and implementation, as well as effective management of existing resources. Banks must understand their markets and ensure that their strategies match customer needs and expectations. They must also monitor results and evaluate their strategies regularly to ensure that they are always meeting their business goals.
2. A bank's business position in the banking industry can be determined by several factors, such as their size, assets, number of customers, product and service portfolio, and reputation. Some banks may have a strong position in the banking industry due to their large size and assets, as well as a large number of customers. These banks may have a wide portfolio of products and services and can offer comprehensive financial solutions to their customers. On the other hand, small banks may have a weaker position in the banking industry, but can have an advantage in providing better personalized service and having closer relationships with their customers. Reputation also plays an important role in determining a bank's business position in the banking industry. Banks that have a good reputation can attract customers and maintain their loyalty, as well as help them attract new business. For example, some banks may have a strong position as a market leader in the banking industry, while others may have a position as a smaller player and focus on a particular market.
3. Achieving a business plan in banking is very important to ensure that banks can meet their goals and objectives. The following are several factors that influence the achievement of business plans in banking: (1) Financial performance; (2) Product and service quality; (3) Risk management; (4) Innovation capability; (5) Market understanding; and (6) Strategy execution.

Second, the bank carries out stress testing on strategy implementation in order to:

 1. Stress testing is a method used by banks to test the implementation of their strategies in difficult or challenging situations. This helps banks understand how their strategies will survive and function when faced with difficult market conditions.
 2. Stress testing involves simulating various scenarios that have the potential to pose risks for banks. These scenarios may involve economic changes, market volatility, or regulatory changes. Banks can use the results of stress tests to validate their strategies and make changes if necessary.
 3. Stress testing also helps banks ensure that they have sufficient resources to overcome difficult situations, and ensure that they have effective risk management. This helps banks ensure that

they can fulfill their obligations to customers and other stakeholders. The results of stress testing should provide feedback to the strategic planning process.

Mapping Literature Review around Strategic Risk Monitoring

Findings in this research topic include:

First, strategic risk monitoring is a process carried out by banks to periodically monitor and evaluate risks related to their business activities. This helps banks ensure that existing risks can be managed properly and ensure the stability of their business.

Second, in terms of strategic risk monitoring, banks monitor risks related to their business strategy. This involves identifying the risks that may arise in the business strategy, determining the acceptable level of risk, and developing risk control measures.

Third, strategic risk monitoring also involves regular evaluation of the risk control actions taken to ensure that these actions are effective and appropriate to changing business situations. This helps banks ensure that the risks associated with their business strategies can be managed properly and ensure the stability of their business.

Mapping Literature Review around Strategic Risk Control

Findings in this research topic include:

First, the definition of strategic risk control, namely a process carried out by banks to manage and reduce risks related to their business activities. This is an important part of risk management that helps banks ensure that the risks they face can be managed well and do not affect the stability of their business.

Second, several steps usually taken in strategic risk control include risk identification, risk assessment, and development of risk control measures. Risk identification involves understanding and mapping the risks that may arise in the banking business. Risk assessment involves determining the level of acceptable risk and the potential impact of that risk. And developing risk control measures involves creating and implementing measures that can minimize risks and ensure that the banking business remains stable.

Third, strategic risk control also requires regular monitoring and evaluation to ensure that the risk control actions taken are effective and appropriate to changes in business situations. This helps banks ensure that the risks they face can be managed well and ensure the stability of their business.

Fourth, Internal Control System. The Internal Control System is a system used by banks to ensure that risks related to their business activities can be managed properly. This internal control system is very important to ensure that banks have good governance and can manage existing risks effectively. The Internal Control System is a system used by banks to ensure that risks related to their business activities can be managed properly. This internal control system is very important to ensure that banks have good governance and can manage existing risks effectively. The internal control system also requires regular monitoring and evaluation to ensure that the risk control actions taken are effective and appropriate to changes in business situations. This helps banks ensure that the risks associated with their business strategies can be managed properly and ensure the stability of their business. The internal control system also requires regular monitoring and evaluation to ensure that the risk control actions taken are effective and appropriate to changes in business situations. This helps banks ensure that the risks associated with their business strategies can be managed properly and ensure the stability of their business.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Strategic Risk Management Information Systems

Findings in this research topic include:

First, the definition of the Strategic Risk Management Information System (SIMRS), namely the system used by banks to monitor and manage risks related to their business activities. This system helps banks determine the level of risk they accept, monitor changes in risk, and evaluate the effectiveness of risk control.

Second, SIMRS consists of various components, including risk identification, risk assessment, risk control and risk monitoring. This system uses advanced tools and technology, such as data analytics and real-time monitoring technology, to help banks understand risk situations and make informed decisions.

Mapping Literature Review around Strategic Risk Mitigation

First, using the IFE-EFE Matrix method to mitigate strategic risk in banking. IFE (Internal Factor Evaluation) and EFE (External Factor Evaluation) matrices are two analytical tools that are useful in evaluating internal and external factors that influence an organization, including banking. In mitigating strategic risks, these two matrices can be used as follows:

- (1) IFE Matrix, which helps banks evaluate internal factors that influence their performance, such as management, resources and technology systems. Banking can assess the level of strengths and weaknesses of each internal factor and prioritize areas that need improvement to minimize risk.
- (2) EFE Matrix, which helps banks evaluate external factors that influence their performance, such as the economic environment, regulations and competition. Banking can assess the level of threats and opportunities from each external factor and prioritize the actions that need to be taken to minimize risks and take advantage of opportunities.

By understanding the factors that influence banking performance and evaluating the level of risk, banks can make more informed and wise decisions to mitigate strategic risks and ensure long-term business sustainability.

Second, the Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) framework is an integrated approach to managing business risks at the company level. This framework can be used to mitigate strategic risks by focusing on several key steps, such as:

- (1) Risk identification, namely the process of determining and assessing risks that may affect the company's strategic objectives. This includes identifying internal and external risks that affect company performance.
- (2) Risk evaluation, namely the process of assessing recognized risks to determine the level of risk to be accepted and the actions needed to mitigate the risk.
- (3) Risk mitigation, namely the process of taking action to minimize risks that affect the company's strategic objectives. This includes implementing risk control strategies, portfolio diversification, and implementing insurance programs.
- (4) Monitoring and review, namely the process of monitoring and reviewing actions taken to ensure that risks have been managed properly and ensure that the actions taken are in accordance with changing business conditions.

Third, Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) is an analysis method used to understand how the elements in a system are related to each other and how they affect overall system performance. In terms of banking, ISM can be used to understand and manage strategic risks by focusing on several key steps, such as:

- (1) Element identification, namely the process of determining factors that influence strategic risk in banking, such as regulations, competition and technological systems.
- (2) Relationship analysis, namely the process of understanding how these factors are related to each other and how they influence banking performance. It helps banks to understand how strategic risks are related to each other and how they affect overall banking performance.
- (3) Priority identification, namely the process of determining the factors that have the greatest influence on strategic risks and prioritizing actions to mitigate risks.
- (4) Action implementation, namely the process of taking action to minimize identified strategic risks, such as portfolio diversification, implementing insurance programs, and improving the internal control system.

Fourth, strategic risk mitigation in Basel III, namely: (1) Basel III emphasizes the importance of strategic risk management and requires banks to implement an effective risk management system and ensure that all levels of management in the organization understand and consider strategic risks; (2) Basel III requires banks to analyze scenarios and ensure that they have adequate response plans to address risks that may occur in the future; (3) Basel III reinforces the importance of portfolio diversification and ensures that banks are not overexposed to certain risks; (4) Basel III requires banks to maintain higher levels of capital to ensure that they have sufficient resources to address possible risks; and (5) Basel III strengthens the importance of transparency and requires banks to report information related to strategic risks openly and transparently to regulators and the public.

Fifth, the Interpretive Structural Modeling approach. The application of this method in strategic risk management is to help analyze the interactions between factors that influence risk and ensure that the actions taken to overcome risk focus on the most significant sources of risk. This approach makes it possible to map the relationships between risk factors and determine priorities in addressing different risks. In the case study, this model is applied to design an integrated strategic risk development model in the banking industry, helping to ensure that risk management focuses on important issues and helps improve banking business performance.

Mapping Literature Review around Other Problems in Strategic Risk

The findings in this research topic are:

First, banks must manage strategic risks associated with new regulations and new sources of competition, by:

- (1) Monitor regulatory developments, namely banks must monitor developments in new regulations and ensure that they understand the implications of these regulations for their business.
- (2) Carrying out risk evaluations, namely banks must evaluate the risks associated with new regulations and new sources of competition, and ensure that they have adequate response plans to address these risks.
- (3) Collaborate with regulators, namely banks must collaborate with regulators and ensure that they understand the new regulations and have sufficient resources to fulfill these regulatory obligations.
- (4) Portfolio diversification, i.e. banks should consider portfolio diversification to minimize risks associated with new regulations and new sources of competition.
- (5) Innovation, namely banks must consider innovation and ensure that they have sufficient resources to meet changing market demands and overcome competition from new sources of competition.
- (6) Strategic risk management, namely banks must have effective strategic risk management and ensure that all levels of management in the organization understand and consider strategic risks.

Second, strategic risk evaluation in the credit process in the banking system can be carried out through the following steps: The first step in strategic risk evaluation is identifying risks that may be related to the credit process. This can involve market analysis, regulations, and business developments. Once risks are identified, banks must conduct risk analysis to understand the implications of these risks for their business. The next step is to assess the risk by considering the severity and probability of the risk occurring. After assessing the risks, banks must have adequate response plans to address the identified risks. This may involve actions such as reducing exposure, increasing control, or diversifying the portfolio. The final step is to carry out regular monitoring and reviews to ensure that risks are still monitored and accepted by the bank. This also helps to ensure that response plans remain relevant and effective. Strategic risk evaluation in the credit process in the banking system is essential to ensure that banks have sufficient resources to address possible risks and ensure that good credit policies and practices are understood and implemented. This helps to ensure that banks remain stable and the credibility of their business is maintained.

Third, strategic risk management is an important prerequisite in conducting feasibility studies on bank mergers and acquisitions. A case study of strategic risk management at the Central Bank of Kenya, the bank's strategic risk management assessment methodology, and the transformation from compliant risk management to strategic risk management are matters that need to be considered in conducting bank mergers and acquisitions. Strategic risk analysis in online banking in India, the role of strategic direction in knowledge risk management and organizational effectiveness, as well as an integrated approach in developing strategic risk models in the banking industry using the Interpretive Structural Modeling approach are also important to understand in strategic risk management in bank mergers and acquisitions.

Fourth, strategic risk management is very important in the online banking (E-Banking) industry because it has many different and complex risks compared to traditional banking models. Risks such as data security, system integrity, and regulatory issues require proper and effective management to minimize negative impacts on the business. Analysis of strategic risks in E-Banking in India and innovative approaches in strategic risk management in the case of Russian banks are very important to

understand in managing strategic risks in E-Banking. The design of an integrated strategic risk development model is also important to ensure that risk management can function well and help improve business performance in the E-Banking industry.

Fifth, innovative approaches to strategic risk management in banking can involve a variety of techniques and methodologies to monitor and address risks arising from internal policies, markets, economics, technology and other factors. Some innovative approaches include: (1) Using data analysis tools such as machine learning and big data to monitor and predict strategic risks; (2) Real-time risk monitoring using technology such as an automatic risk monitoring system that can provide information and early warning about potential risks; (3) Use of simulation models to predict how external and internal changes will affect the banking business and determine actions to overcome risks; (4) Collaboration with stakeholders such as regulators, business partners and shareholders to address strategic risks together; and (5) Scenario analysis to understand how potential changes in the business environment will affect risks and prepare actions to address those risks.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding strategic risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions during the period 1981 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 89 research articles, with 19 international journals indexed by Scopus and 70 international and national journals indexed by Sinta.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding strategic risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions are divided into 13 clusters and 88 items. Cluster 1 consists of 13 items, cluster 2 consists of 12 items, cluster 3 consists of 11 items, cluster 4 consists of 10 items, cluster 5 consists of 8 items, cluster 6 consists of 6 items, cluster 7 consists of 6 items, cluster 8 consists of 5 items, cluster 9 consists of 5 items, cluster 10 consists of 4 items, cluster 11 consists of 3 items, cluster 12 consists of 3 items, and cluster 13 consists of 2 items.
- Based on a literature review, there are 11 main research themes surrounding strategic risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely: (1) Definition and objectives of risk; (2) Risk monitoring; (3) Risk strategy; (4) Risk levels, policies, procedures and limits; (5) Risk identification; (6) Risk measurement; (7) Risk monitoring; (8) Risk control; (9) Risk information system; (10) Risk mitigation; and (11) Other issues related to strategic risk.

is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- The results of the e- review literature study can be explained in a more complex way.

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